

Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology®

RESEARCH ARTICLE

10.1029/2024PA005063

Key Points:

- Using synchrotron radiation X-ray microcomputed tomography (SR μ CT), we established 3D morphology models of benthic foraminifera
- Foraminiferal morphology, assemblage, and geochemistry as a multiproxy approach to reconstruct oxygen and salinity conditions in the LIG
- Foraminifera morphology (e.g., pore patterns, thickness, proloculus) changed, to optimize function under varying oxygen and salinity stress

Supporting Information:

Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Correspondence to:

S. Ni,
sha.ni@uni-hamburg.de

Citation:

Ni, S., M \ddot{u} ter, D., Charrieau, L. M., Pirzamanbein, B., Choquel, C., Knudsen, K. L., et al. (2025). Morphological insights from benthic foraminifera for environmental conditions in the Baltic Sea during the last interglacial. *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology*, 40, e2024PA005063. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024PA005063>

Received 8 NOV 2024

Accepted 4 MAR 2025

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization: Sha Ni, Helena L. Filipsson

Data curation: Sha Ni, Dirk M \ddot{u} ter

Formal analysis: Sha Ni, Laurie M. Charrieau

Funding acquisition: Karen Luise Knudsen, Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz, Helena L. Filipsson

Investigation: Sha Ni, Dirk M \ddot{u} ter, Laurie M. Charrieau, Behnaz Pirzamanbein, Constance Choquel, Karen Luise Knudsen, Helena L. Filipsson

Morphological Insights From Benthic Foraminifera for Environmental Conditions in the Baltic Sea During the Last Interglacial

Sha Ni^{1,2}

¹Department of Geology, Lund University, Lund, Sweden, ²Institute for Geology, Hamburg University, Hamburg, Germany, ³FORCE Technology, Br \ddot{o} ndby, Denmark, ⁴MARUM, Bremen, Germany, ⁵Department of Statistics, Lund University, Lund, Sweden, ⁶Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography (MIO), Aix-Marseille University, Marseille, France, ⁷Department of Geoscience, Aarhus University, Aarhus, Denmark

Abstract Marine environments worldwide are increasingly threatened by warming, deoxygenation, and ocean acidification. These stressors can be recorded as alterations in foraminiferal geochemistry and morphology. We integrated morphological features with assemblage and geochemical records of benthic foraminifera from the Danish Straits at the entrance to the Baltic Sea, covering the Last Interglacial period (LIG, MIS5e), to assess potential indications of environmental changes. Using synchrotron radiation X-ray microcomputed tomography (SR μ CT), we measured *Elphidium clavatum* in terms of diameter, height, surface area, volume, thickness, and number of pores. Pore patterns and wall thickness were evaluated simultaneously to assess both metabolic and mechanical constraints under environmental changes. The proloculus (initial chamber) size may indicate the reproduction mode of foraminifera in response to environmental stress, including salinity and oxygen variations. We show that during the early-mid LIG, the physical resistance of *E. clavatum* against mechanical constraints remained relatively strong, characterized by high wall thickness and low porosity, coinciding with higher bottom water salinity and oxygen content. In the mid-late LIG, pore density and wall thickness decreased, while porosity and proloculus size increased, fueling metabolism and increasing survival rates. These traits reflect adaptation to an increasingly stressful environment with lower salinity and oxygen levels, as indicated by declining faunal diversity and increasing *E. clavatum* abundance. Our study demonstrates that benthic foraminiferal morphological features, including proloculus size, wall thickness, and pore patterns, serve as indicators for assessing stress levels and reconstructing bottom water conditions in brackish and potentially hypoxic environments during the LIG.

Plain Language Summary Global marine environments are increasingly threatened by warming, reduced oxygen, and ocean acidification. Foraminifera, tiny single-celled organisms often with shells of calcium carbonates, can reflect environmental stress through changes recorded in their shell chemistry and shape. In this study, we examined foraminifera from the Baltic Sea entrance during the Last Interglacial period (LIG). We focused on one species *Elphidium clavatum*, analyzing the size, surface area, volume, thickness, and pores of the shell using advanced imaging techniques. By looking at pore patterns and shell thickness, we assessed metabolic and mechanical resilience in changing environments. In the early to mid-LIG, *E. clavatum* was subjected to strong mechanical constraints, with thicker shells and low porosity, coinciding with higher salinity and oxygen levels. However, as conditions became more stressful in the mid-late LIG, with decreasing salinity and oxygen, *E. clavatum* adapted by increasing its initial chamber size and porosity while reducing shell thickness. These changes enhanced the oxygen uptake and survival rates. Our study highlights the role of morphological features, including initial chamber size, shell thickness, and pore patterns, as indicators for assessing stress levels and reconstructing past water conditions in low salinity and oxygen environments.

1. Introduction

The investigation of benthic foraminiferal geochemistry and morphology remains pivotal in unraveling the intricate dynamics of past marine environments and understanding the long-term variations in ocean environmental conditions. The geochemical composition of foraminiferal tests (shells), that is, the elemental and isotopic compositions (e.g., Mg/Ca, Ba/Ca, Mn/Ca, I/Ca, carbon and oxygen isotopes) in the calcium carbonate of the

© 2025. The Author(s).

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Methodology: Sha Ni, Dirk Mütter, Behnaz Pirzamanbein, Constance Choquel, Helena L. Filipsson
Project administration: Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz, Helena L. Filipsson
Software: Sha Ni, Dirk Mütter, Behnaz Pirzamanbein
Supervision: Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz, Helena L. Filipsson
Validation: Dirk Mütter, Constance Choquel, Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz, Helena L. Filipsson
Visualization: Sha Ni, Behnaz Pirzamanbein
Writing – original draft: Sha Ni
Writing – review & editing: Sha Ni, Dirk Mütter, Laurie M. Charrieau, Behnaz Pirzamanbein, Constance Choquel, Karen Luise Knudsen, Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz, Helena L. Filipsson

tests serves as a powerful proxy for deciphering changes in seawater chemistry, temperature, salinity, and oxygenation states (e.g., Gingele & Dahmke, 1994; Groeneveld et al., 2018; Groeneveld & Filipsson, 2013; Hönisch et al., 2011; Lu et al., 2022; Ni et al., 2020; Pearson, 2012). Recent advancements in imaging technology, notably micro-CT (micro-computed tomography), provide a non-destructive and comprehensive approach to studying diverse aspects of foraminiferal test morphology, such as test volume, wall thickness, surface area, and pore patterns (e.g., Choquel et al., 2023; Iwasaki et al., 2015; Johnstone et al., 2010; Kinoshita et al., 2021; Kuroyanagi et al., 2021; Titelboim et al., 2021; Zarkogiannis et al., 2022). These morphological parameters, reflecting the conditions in which foraminiferal specimens lived, offer valuable insights into the organisms' responses to environmental changes. Specific features include those influenced by the *in situ* calcification environment, such as test size coefficient (indicated by test diameter squared and test height), number of chambers, surface area, volume, and mass. It also includes features influenced by the carbonate saturation state of the environment, in which the foraminifera were deposited.

The pore patterns of the tests (pore size: area of individual pores, porosity: total pore area per unit size, and pore density: number of pores per unit surface) and wall thickness observed in tests of foraminifera are frequently associated with the organism's respiratory capabilities, encompassing gas exchange processes, notably involving oxygen (e.g., Burke et al., 2018; Davis et al., 2021). Higher porosity and a thinner test wall result in wider and shorter pathways for gas exchange between seawater and the cell. Several studies show that the pore features and test wall thickness are related to dissolved oxygen concentration and water dynamic situations (e.g., Glock et al., 2012; Gupta & Machain-Castillo, 1993; Kuhnt et al., 2013, 2014; Moodley & Hess, 1992; Rathburn et al., 2018; Wetmore, 1987). Greater porosity can essentially be achieved by increasing pore density and/or pore size (e.g., Govindankutty Menon et al., 2023), however, the highest porosity can be reached by increasing pore radius, since the porosity is much more sensitive to changes in pore size than in pore numbers (Richirt et al., 2019). Alterations in pore patterns serve as a metric for discerning fluctuations in oxygen concentrations within the marine environment (Glock et al., 2011, 2018, 2022; Lu et al., 2022; Petersen et al., 2016; Rathburn et al., 2018; Tetard et al., 2017). In oxygen-depleted environments, thin-wall species strongly dominate foraminiferal assemblages (e.g., Bernhard, 1986; Gupta & Machain-Castillo, 1993; Kaiho, 1994).

Variations in pore size, porosity, pore density, and wall thickness are linked to both gas exchange (metabolic demands of the cell) and test robustness (mechanical integrity of the test, i.e., the mechanical stress at which test failure occurs) (Richirt et al., 2019). However, in previous studies, the mechanical resistance of foraminiferal tests including wall thickness and maximum physical strength of the test has rarely been considered, although it is also strongly influenced by the pore patterns (Richirt et al., 2019). The relationships between the pore size, pore density, porosity, and mechanical stress limit when the test collapses are based on the assumptions: (a) overall foraminiferal porosity reflects the intensity of gas exchanges, which is determined by cell volume, cell metabolic demand, gas concentrations in the surrounding seawater, and (b) there is a mechanical constraint (minimum test robustness) that limits the increase in overall porosity since the porosity is inversely correlated with test robustness (Richirt et al., 2019). However, these changes of pore patterns and test wall thickness depend on the balance between metabolic demand and mechanical integrity. Consequently, foraminiferal pore patterns and test wall thickness can be potentially used as proxies for reconstructing oxygen levels and general ambient physical stresses.

Foraminiferal proloculus (i.e., initial chamber) formation varies with the mode of reproduction (i.e., sexual or asexual). In sexual reproduction, foraminifera produce microspheric proloculi, while asexual reproduction, which involves mitotic cell division, leads to megalospheric proloculi, which are typically larger (e.g., Goldstein, 1999; Hallock, 1985; Murray, 2006). Asexual reproduction enables rapid population growth under stable and stressful conditions, sexual reproduction provides resilience in fluctuating environments by promoting genetic variation, which is crucial for long-term adaptation (Armstrong & Brasier, 2005; Murray, 2006). Therefore, the proloculus size can potentially also be used as an evaluation factor for the stability and stress level of environmental conditions.

We infer a positive correlation between the foraminiferal diversity and oxygen concentration since low oxygen concentrations can lead to low diversity and dominance of a few opportunistic species due to physiological stress on taxa (Levin et al., 2001; Schmiedl et al., 2023). Consequently, we could use bottom water salinity (in such a brackish water environment, reconstructed by using foraminiferal Mg/Ca and stable oxygen isotopes, Ni et al., 2021), foraminiferal diversity, and the flux (total number of individuals/cm²/year) of opportunistic

Figure 1. Map of southwestern Baltic Sea-North Sea region showing the study site Mommark. The base map is generated from GeoMapApp. The star represents the Mommark site while the dashed lines indicate the presumed LIG coastline in the region of the entrance of the Baltic Sea modified from Kristensen and Knudsen (2006).

foraminiferal species such as *Elphidium clavatum* (cf. Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006) to evaluate the environmental stress levels affecting foraminifera. Furthermore, we could assess their correlation with morphological parameters, including proloculus size, pore patterns and test wall thickness. The integration of both geochemical and morphological analyses of foraminiferal tests presents a powerful and comprehensive approach to reconstructing past marine environmental conditions.

The Last Interglacial (LIG) has been extensively studied across marine and terrestrial sites in the northern European region, shedding light on its dynamic characteristics and environmental changes (e.g., Andrn et al., 2011; Brewer et al., 2008; Cheddadi et al., 1998; Knudsen et al., 2009). The LIG (130–115 ka BP) was marked by a relatively warmer climate than the present, associated with higher salinity and higher sea levels in the Baltic Sea (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006). The Mommark site is located in southern Denmark at the entrance of the Baltic Sea (Figure 1); its marine sequence represents a brackish water environment from the LIG period. The interplay of geological and climatic factors during the LIG left distinct imprints on the landscape and the sedimentary and microfossil archives in the area (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006; Ni et al., 2021). Due to isostatic movements, sea level changes, and variations in hydrography in this region, seasonal temperature and salinity changes at Mommark were considerably lower during the LIG than seen in the region today based on benthic foraminiferal geochemistry (Mg/Ca, Ba/Ca, Mn/Ca, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of *E. clavatum*) and climate model simulations (Ni et al., 2021, 2023). In the southern Baltic Sea region, the bottom water at Mommark was generally more oxygen-depleted based on foraminiferal - and mollusc faunas, and foraminiferal Mn/Ca (Funder & Balic-Zunic, 2006; Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006; Ni et al., 2021). Moreover, the seasonal climate variation in the Danish Straits region during the LIG is considered larger and more fluctuating than the modern conditions (Andrn et al., 2011).

Our study aims to elucidate the relationship between foraminiferal test morphology and past hydrographic conditions in the Baltic Sea, assessing the potential of these morphological parameters as paleoclimate proxies. We employed synchrotron radiation X-ray microtomography (SR μ CT) to generate high-resolution 3D models of foraminiferal tests, providing a complete, undistorted view of the structure, avoiding deformation and allowing for precise analysis of internal and external features from multiple angles. We integrate morphological data with paleoenvironmental reconstructions based on benthic fauna assemblages and foraminiferal geochemical compositions. This comprehensive approach provides a holistic perspective on the interaction between foraminiferal morphological indicators and the marine environment during the LIG, providing valuable insights concerning

ongoing discussions on climate change impacts on marine ecosystems and the adaptive responses of foraminifera to environmental stress.

2. Methods and Material

2.1. Study Site and Age Model

We used samples from the Mommark site located next to the Danish Straits (Figure 1). This site is today on land as an outcrop (54°55.7'N, 10°02.7'E), but it was a shallow-marine setting during the LIG (Eiriksson et al., 2006). The sediments at the Mommark site are composed of non-laminated greenish-gray silty clay to clay (the *Cyprina* Clay), with the silty clays occurring in the lower transitional part of the marine sequence (Eiriksson et al., 2006; Knudsen et al., 2011; Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006). Our study is based on material collected in connection with the BALTEEM Project, 1998–2001 (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006).

During the LIG, the Mommark site had a near-coastal shallow-water setting, where the paleo-water depth was shallower than 30 m (Gibbard & Glaister, 2006). A pollen chronology was established for the Mommark site (Gibbard & Glaister, 2006) and the local pollen zones are correlated to the regional pollen zones in Denmark (Andersen, 1975) and assigned to a chronology by integration with the annually laminated lacustrine sequence from Bispingen, northern Germany (Müller, 1974). The core covers a period of about 10.5 ka since the beginning of the LIG.

2.2. Foraminiferal Morphology Micro-CT Measurement

We randomly picked 6–10 *E. clavatum* specimens within the 150–355 μm size fraction from 14 age intervals in the Mommark sediment outcrop (in total 122 specimens, Table S1). To study the morphological changes in the fossil record, we collected SR μ CT data sets during two synchrotron sessions at SPring-8, Hyogo prefecture, Japan. We mounted the specimens on HiTaCa®, a carbon nanotube (CNT) sheet (Hitachi Zosen Corporation; Fujimoto et al., 2018), to avoid damaging the tests during handling, facilitate test recovery, and enable 3D reconstructions (Choquel et al., 2023). We used the microtomography setup at the beamline BL47XU, achieving a voxel size of 500 nm (2019 experiment) and 385 nm (2021 experiment), with 1800 projections and 150 ms exposure time at 23 keV X-ray energy. We performed the measurements in ambient conditions with no further equipment.

We reconstructed and segmented all data sets (Otsu thresholding), and constructed 3D surface meshes from the segmented data using a Marching Cubes algorithm (isosurface) in ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012). *E. clavatum*, the foraminiferal species used in this study, has a discus-shape biconvex test. The foraminifera scans can be arbitrarily oriented, and the largest cross-section can be aligned to lie within one single slice of the CT image stack. On this slice, the whole foraminiferal diameter (a in Figure 2), the ultimate chamber diameter, and the proloculus diameter were measured using ImageJ's measuring tool. The average test wall thickness was calculated using the *BoneJ* plugin in ImageJ on the segmented data set (Choquel et al., 2023; Domander et al., 2021). Using the surface mesh, geometrical and topological properties can be extracted in Meshlab (Choquel et al., 2023; Cignoni et al., 2008). The surface area is the sum of the areas of the triangular surfaces comprising the mesh. The volume is the volume contained inside the surface mesh. Pores are assumed to be topological holes going through the mesh. The total number of these topological holes (i.e., pores) was calculated in Meshlab (2023.12 version) (method as in Choquel et al., 2023). Parameters counted or measured from 3D models of SR μ CT scans are shown in Table 1.

2.3. Size-Adjustment

The test sizes of the foraminifera (i.e., diameter, in a range of 158–398 μm ; height, in a range of 69–205 μm) show significant positive correlations with volume (in a range of $0.4\text{--}5.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ mm}^3$), surface area ($0.2\text{--}1.3 \text{ mm}^2$), number of pores (284–8,016), number of chambers (8–23), average test wall thickness (3.5–10.6 μm , equals to $\sim 1\text{--}5\%$ of diameter), and ultimate chamber diameter. These parameters are significantly correlated with one another, except for wall thickness and number of pores, which show no significant correlation (Figures S1 and S2 in Supporting Information S1). The surface area/volume ratios are in a range of 224–641. These parameters are highly related to the foraminiferal size coefficient (i.e., $\text{diameter}^2 \cdot \text{height}$, Table S2) due to ontogenetic effect. Therefore, to minimize the ontogenetic effect on morphological parameters, we use the size-adjusted parameters

Figure 2. A 3D view and edited SR μ CT scan image slices as examples of the cross-section and longitudinal section of the foraminifera showing (a) diameter (red solid line), (b) ultimate chamber diameter (blue solid line), (c) proloculus, that is, initial chamber diameter (yellow solid line) in the cross-section, and (d) height (green dashed line) in the longitudinal section and a simplified perspective sketch of a foraminifera test with a green dashed line showing its height.

(mass, volume, surface area, thickness, number of pores and chambers, ultimate chamber diameter, and porosity) for the analyses. Since surface area/volume and pore density (number of pores per surface area) are per-unit ratios, there is no need for size adjustment. The proloculus chamber diameters are not adjusted to size since they are the initial chambers.

Table 1

Name of Morphological Variables Used in This Study

Morphological parameter	Definition	Data type
Diameter	The longest distance across a whole specimen, where the cross section is the largest (a in Figure 2)	Measured
Ultimate chamber diameter	The longest distance from the penultimate chamber to ultimate chamber, along the test's growing direction (b in Figure 2)	Measured
Proloculus diameter	The initial chamber diameter (c in Figure 2)	Measured
Height	The distance measured from the middle part of the longitudinal section (d in Figure 2)	Measured
Number of chambers	Total number of chambers of a whole specimen	Measured & size-adjusted
Thickness	The average test wall thickness of a whole specimen	Measured & size-adjusted
Surface area	The total surface area of a whole specimen, including the outer surface, inner surface, the interfaces between the chambers, and pore wall surface	Measured & size-adjusted
Volume	The total volume of the test, excluding pores	Measured & size-adjusted
Mass	The total mass of the test. Volume * Density (2.7 g/cm ³)	Estimated & calculated & size-adjusted
Number of pores	Total number of pores of a whole specimen	Measured & size-adjusted
Pore density	Total number of pores per total surface area	Measured & size-adjusted
Porosity	Total pore area of a whole specimen (only available in the form of size-adjusted and 0–1 normalized values, no absolute value available)	Estimated & calculated & size-adjusted

Note. Data type—measured means the parameter was measured directly in the software from SR μ CT scans; method—estimated and calculated means the parameter was not directly from scans but calculated based on estimation using other parameters.

2.4. Data Normalization and Statistical Analyses

We rescaled the morphological parameters to values between zero and one for statistical analyses using the min-max normalization equation:

$$X_{\text{normalized}} = (X - X_{\text{min}}) / (X_{\text{max}} - X_{\text{min}})$$

where X is the value of a morphological parameter for individuals, $X_{\text{normalized}}$ is the normalized value in a range of 0–1, X_{min} is the minimum value of all individuals and X_{max} is the maximum value of all individuals.

All correlation analyses between two variables were conducted using data from the same age intervals. If age intervals were missing for certain measurements, we performed linear interpolation. We applied the Shapiro-Wilk normality test to determine whether the variable comes from a normally distributed population. In each age interval, we used the median values to represent the data from each depth for the analyses to avoid the effect of nonnormal distribution. We performed Pearson's correlation test on variables that both are normally distributed, whereas for the data sets with nonnormal distribution, Spearman's correlation test was applied. We used 0–1 normalized data sets for all correlation and trend tests. For the correlation tests between each two morphological parameters, we used individual measurements (122 specimens). To calculate the diversity of the foraminiferal assemblage (counts from Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006) we used the Shannon H diversity (Shannon, 1948). We performed the Mann-Kendall trend test for determining variable time-series trends (Gilbert, 1987). We considered $P < 0.05$ as significant. For the parametric data set we tested equality of variance using the F -test before applying the t -test, we used an independent t -test when the data has equal variances, otherwise, Welch's t -test was used. For parameters of two proloculus groups (i.e., microspheric and megalospheric), we applied the Mann-Whitney U test regardless of normality and variance assumptions. We performed Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to explore the correlations between variables and their contribution to each principal component (PC). All statistical analyses are performed in R (version 4.4.1) and shown in Table S2.

2.5. Parameter Calculation

Parameters not directly measured but calculated and estimated based on other measurements are shown in Table 1. To estimate the mass, we used the volume of the mesh and assumed that calcite to be the only constituent (density: 2.7 g/cm^3 , Takahashi & Allan, 1984). This is reasonable as the organic lining is thin and thus does not contribute much to the volume. Furthermore, the test density of the foraminifera, which is related to the gray values in the CT images, seems rather uniform such that any other mineral constituents would have to be of similar density and thus not interfere with the mass estimation. Pore density (PD) is calculated as the number of pores per total surface area. It is important to note that the total surface area used in PD calculation includes S_{in} , S_{out} and the pore wall surface area (i.e., the pore wall area of V_1 and V_2 in Figure 3c). Porosity is estimated assuming that inner surface and outer surface of foraminifera can be considered $S_{\text{in}} \approx S_{\text{out}}$ (Figure 3), as wall thickness (t) \ll chamber diameter. Test calcite volume equals to a hypothetical total surface area (S_{surface}) multiply the wall thickness, $V_{\text{calcite}} = S_{\text{surface}} * t$ (notice that S_{surface} excludes the pore wall surface area), $S_{\text{surface}} = V_{\text{calcite}}/t$. The normalized and size-adjusted S_{surface} is complementary to the size-adjusted total pore (defined as porosity in this study), which can be estimated as size-adjusted and 0–1 normalized $S_{\text{pore}} = 1 - S_{\text{surface}}$. The test robustness we evaluated in this study is defined as the mechanical stress limit (σ , i.e., the mechanical stress at which test failure occurs, Figure 3a), which is inversely correlated with the pore size (with a relationship of $\sigma = r^{-1/2}$ in the model of Richirt et al., 2019).

3. Results

3.1. Proloculus Types

Several morphological features are related to foraminiferal reproductive strategy and life cycles, and these features may correlate due to ontogenetic effects (i.e., size-adjusted parameters in 2.3). The final test size of each foraminiferal specimen (i.e., diameter; Figure 2a) shows a statistically significant correlation with the proloculus diameter (Figure 2c). About 7% of the total 122 scanned specimens have a proloculus smaller than $16 \mu\text{m}$ (in the range of $11\text{--}15 \mu\text{m}$, here defined as microspheric individuals, 9 specimens), and most proloculus diameters fall in

Figure 3. Sketches representing *E. clavatum* chambers illustrating different test surface area and pore area: (a) larger pore area with smaller surface area; (b) smaller pore area with larger surface area. S_{in} : total surface area of the inner surface of the chamber; S_{out} : total surface area of the outer surface of the chamber; σ : mechanical stress limit of the test. Modified from Richirt et al. (2019); (c) a zoom-in sketch on the pore area comparing different pore sizes corresponding to different pore areas on the test. t : average wall thickness; r_1 and S_1 : radius and pore area of a larger pore₁ as in (a); r_2 and S_2 : radius and pore area of a smaller pore₂ as in (b).

the range of 24–65 μm (here defined as megalospheric individuals, 112 specimens) (Figure 4). One individual has a large proloculus ($\sim 88 \mu\text{m}$, also defined as a megalospheric individual).

The proloculus diameter accounts for $\sim 6\%$ of the total test diameter in the microspheric group and 15% in the megalospheric group. We compared all morphological parameters (not size-adjusted or 0–1 normalized) between microspheric and megalospheric individuals, and only the mean total number of pores and test wall thickness show no significant difference (Table S2, Figure 4). Foraminifera from the megalospheric group has a significantly larger diameter, mass (volume), surface area, wall thickness, and ultimate chamber diameter. However, the microspheric individuals formed more chambers (an average difference of +4 chambers), and the surface area/volume ratios are higher compared to those of the megalospheric group.

3.2. Relationships Between Size-Adjusted Morphological Parameters

The size-adjusted volume and mass of the test can be mainly controlled by two parameters: (a) total volume of the pore lumen, the larger the pores, the lower the overall calcite test volume and mass; (b) thickness of the wall, the thinner the wall, the lower the volume (Figure 3). Size-adjusted volume and mass are inversely correlated with the porosity and positively correlated with the wall thickness (Figure S3 in Supporting Information S1). The proloculus diameter is only positively correlated with the porosity, and these two are inversely correlated with the other parameters (size-adjusted wall thickness, surface area, surface/volume, number of pores and chambers, ultimate chamber diameter). The size-adjusted wall thickness is inversely correlated with porosity (Figure 5a) but positively correlated with the pore density and size-adjusted number of pores. The porosity is inversely correlated to the pore density and size-adjusted number of pores (Figure 5b). The size-related parameters (as explained in Section 2.3) discussed later on are referred to size-adjusted and 0–1 normalized data.

The size-adjusted morphological parameters of each age interval can be distinguished into three groups based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) results (Figure S4 in Supporting Information S1):

Figure 4. Distribution of the diameter of (a) proloculus versus ultimate chambers (i.e., initial and last chambers) and (b) proloculus (i.e., initial chamber) versus the whole test; (c) proloculus (initial chamber) versus the test mass. Red and blue dots indicate microspheric and megalospheric individuals, respectively. The dashed lines are the trend lines for these two groups; (d) box plots of morphological parameters of microspheric (“micro”) and megalospheric (“mega”) groups in red and blue, respectively. Red and blue dots are the outliers based on 1.5 Interquartile range. Between microspheric and megalospheric groups, only the number of pores and test wall thickness show no significant difference ($p = 0.075$ and 0.067 , respectively), the other parameters show significant differences between two groups. Results of Mann-Whitney U test for rank comparison between groups are shown with a significant level on top of the box plots: *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$. Equations and correlation coefficients see Table S2.

Group 1: size-adjusted wall thickness, number of chambers and pores, surface area, and ultimate chamber diameter, pore number per surface area and surface area/volume ratios are inversely correlated with Group 2: porosity (size-adjusted total pore area) and proloculus diameter. All these parameters in Groups 1 & 2 together may represent PC1 that explain 73% of the variance; Group 3: size-adjusted mass, show no correlation with other parameters, since it is highly dependent on size and all size-related parameters are size-adjusted (see Section 2.3).

Figure 5. Correlations of size-adjusted and normalized pore patterns and wall thickness: (a) porosity versus wall thickness; (b) pore density versus porosity. The gray dots show the actual measured data points; the black dots are the median values of each age interval with error bars indicating one standard error (SE). The black lines are linear regression based on the median of each age interval. Equations and correlation coefficients see Table S2.

bottom water conditions at Mommark related to constantly low oxygen and salinity conditions. At such a shallow site in the entrance of the Baltic Sea, Danish Straits, foraminifera are subjected to varying conditions due to the alternate influence of saline North Sea inflows and brackish Baltic Sea outflows (water depth <30 m, Ni et al., 2021). The variation in environmental conditions may not be substantial enough to drive the species to shift predominantly to sexual reproduction. The proloculus diameters are inversely correlated with the size-adjusted wall thickness, ultimate chamber diameters, number of chambers, surface area, and the diversity which coinciding with unfavorable environmental conditions with lower salinity and oxygen concentrations, result in larger proloculi but weaker test structures (i.e., thinner walls and smaller and fewer chambers). It indicates that when the diversity was low under such a stressful environment, *E. clavatum* asexually reproduced larger juveniles (megalospheric individuals) as an adaptation to improve its survival. The dominance of asexual-megalospheric individuals in the reproduction mode suggests that during the LIG, *E. clavatum* survived better under the environmental conditions, requiring less genetic diversity. However, under conditions of higher hydrodynamics (such as stronger Baltic inflows and outflows at a shallow coastal site with increased current velocity and greater wave

3.3. Morphological Variations During the LIG

The morphology of the foraminiferal specimens from Mommark changed markedly over the Last Interglacial period (LIG) (Figure 6). The surface area/volume ratios and size-adjusted surface area show significant decreasing trends during the LIG. In general, the variations of parameters are greater during the first half of the LIG (128–123 ka BP) compared to the latter half (123–119 ka BP). We observe a higher abundance of pores but smaller total pore area and thicker walls during the first half LIG but thinner walls with a larger total pore area and fewer pores during the latter half LIG. During the early LIG (128–126 ka BP), the ultimate chamber diameter, surface area, number of chambers, and wall thickness increased. During the late LIG (121–119 ka BP), the proloculus were relatively larger (Figure 6a), coinciding with smaller final chambers, and fewer chambers (Figures 6b and 6c). Meanwhile, pore density, number of pores, and the wall thickness (Figures 6h–6j) were relatively low, while the porosity was high (Figure 6g).

4. Discussions

4.1. Morphological Variations

4.1.1. Reproduction-Related Morphological Variation

The morphological parameters (i.e., diameter, height, volume, surface area, number of chambers, ultimate chamber diameter, surface area/volume) are significantly different between microspheric and megalospheric groups, except for the wall thickness and number of pores which show no significant difference (Figure 4d). It indicates that general test allometry, which is involved in calcitic test formation and the life cycle, is mainly controlled by reproduction and proloculus types.

Even though the average diameter and ultimate chamber diameters of microspheric and megalospheric specimens are significantly different, they overlap. Microspheric individuals have smaller ultimate chamber diameters but more chambers to reach the same range of diameters, meaning that we cannot determine the proloculus type based on diameter or vice versa. However, we could potentially use proloculus diameter range and megalospheric/microspheric individual ratios for evaluating environmental stress levels. Environmental stress (e.g., oxygen, salinity, temperature, and food availability) can lead to a higher frequency of asexual reproduction in foraminifera, often characterized by the formation of megalospheric proloculi that are more resilient in suboptimal conditions (e.g., Hallock, 1985; Murray, 2006). In general, we observe much fewer microspheric individuals than megalospheric ones (9 vs. 113 individuals) during the LIG due to unfavorable

Figure 6. Distribution scatter and 0–1 normalized median values of morphological parameters at each age interval: left panel: (a) proloculus (i.e., initial chamber) diameter; 0–1 normalized and size-adjusted (b) ultimate chamber diameter; (c) number of chambers; (d) surface area; (e) mass (same as volume); right panel: 0–1 normalized (f) surface area/volume ratios; and wall thickness and pore pattern related parameters: (h) pore density (number of pores per surface area); 0–1 normalized and size-adjusted (g) porosity (estimated total pore area); (i) number of pores; (j) wall thickness. The gray dots show the actual measured data points; the black dots are the median values of each age interval.

action) and resources-related stress (such as fluctuations in nutrients and food availability), rapid population expansion was necessary (Armstrong & Brasier, 2005; Murray, 2006). Nevertheless, further study is needed to fully understand the roles of specific environmental stressors and the adaptive strategies of foraminifera reproductive modes.

4.1.2. Pore Pattern-Related Morphological Variation

We compared *E. clavatum* pore patterns (pore density and porosity), and wall thickness to environmental conditions and foraminiferal assemblage data to investigate the oxygen demand for metabolism and mechanical constraints (i.e., oxygen availability and test robustness, Figure 7). The estimated porosity (calculated as size-adjusted total pore area) shows a significant inverse correlation with several morphological parameters, including pore density, wall thickness, number of chambers, surface area, and ultimate chamber diameter. It also inversely correlates with environmental factors such as bottom water salinity, foraminiferal diversity, and therefore oxygen content. The porosity is positively correlated with *E. clavatum* flux and carbon isotopes ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) during the LIG (Table S2, Figure S5 in Supporting Information S1). It demonstrates that test robustness may decrease with decreasing salinity and oxygen level, to prioritize gas exchange (to maintain a nominal metabolic activity). The mechanical integrity of the test was reduced, and pore radius was increased, to enhance metabolic efficiency by optimizing the gas exchange in response to low oxygen availability. Meanwhile, the pore density decreased to avoid substantially diminishing the test robustness. Our results agree with the model (Richirt et al., 2019) showing that to simultaneously meet metabolic needs and preserve the mechanical integrity of the test, foraminifera increase their porosity by enlarging the pore size while reducing the pore density.

Figure 7. (a) reconstructed bottom water salinity based on foraminiferal Mg/Ca and oxygen isotopes (Ni et al., 2021), (b) *E. clavatum* Ba/Ca (Ni et al., 2021); (c) foraminiferal diversity (*Shannon_H* index), (d) *E. clavatum* carbon isotopes (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006); (e) reconstructed bottom water temperature (Ni et al., 2021); (f) *E. clavatum* flux (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006: as *Elphidium excavatum*); normalized foraminiferal test: (g) proloculus (initial chamber) diameter, (h) surface area/volume ratios; size-adjusted and 0–1 normalized foraminiferal test: (i) porosity (size-adjusted pore area), (j) pore density (size-adjusted number of pores), and (k) wall thickness. The blue and pink shadow bars correspond to LIG sub-periods (early mid LIG and mid-late LIG, respectively).

The flux of *E. clavatum* was relatively higher when diversity and salinity decreased, indicating that *E. clavatum* has an advantage over other species under low salinity and potentially low oxygen conditions. This may be linked to its high nutritional and habitat versatility, as well as its capability to quickly colonize a harsh environment when overall taxa stress/competition is relatively low (Polyak et al., 2002, ref. therein). The inverse correlation between *E. clavatum* flux and pore density, along with the positive correlation between *E. clavatum* flux and porosity, implies the pore pattern adaptation of *E. clavatum* is an effective strategy for supporting population growth.

4.2. Environmental Indication During the LIG

In general, the morphological parameters and environmental conditions show variability during the LIG at Mommark. The bottom water salinity, foraminifera diversity, *E. clavatum* size-adjusted ultimate chamber diameter, and surface area show decreasing trends throughout the LIG (Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006: as *Elphidium excavatum*; Ni et al., 2021, Figure S6 in Supporting Information S1). During the LIG, Mn/Ca of *E. clavatum* from the Mommark site was ~3–4 times higher (with a mean value of 0.55 mmol/mol) than that from the other locations of the straits and the southern Baltic, indicating a generally oxygen-depleted environment (Ni

et al., 2021). The bottom water temperature shows no significant correlation with foraminiferal morphological parameters. Since ~126 ka BP, the ultimate chamber diameter, wall thickness, and surface area of *E. clavatum* show overall decreasing trends, while porosity exhibits an increasing trend. The changes in wall thickness and porosity suggest a reduction in test robustness and an increase in gas exchange to sustain nominal metabolic activity. This pattern aligns with an increasing environmental stress level, as indicated by declining bottom water salinity, foraminiferal diversity, and oxygen levels (Figure 7). Calcification can be influenced by carbonate variability and bottom water saturation state, which is linked to Ca^{2+} concentrations and salinity in the Baltic Sea (Tyrrell et al., 2008; Umling et al., 2021). It aligns with our results, suggesting that the lower bottom water salinity could have been associated with a reduced saturation state, potentially decreasing calcification and resulting in forming thinner tests and larger pores. It implies that the bottom water conditions became more challenging for foraminifera assemblages in general at the entrance of the Baltic Sea. The surface area/volume ratios exhibit a decreasing trend throughout the LIG, indicating that foraminiferal tests became larger and/or smoother and/or developed more complex test structures (i.e., an increased number of chambers and/or higher porosity). The potential Surface area/Volume-indication of test smoothness may be explained by more dynamic environments, foraminifera may evolve smoother tests to reduce bottom water drag, thereby lowering their S/V ratios, however, further investigation is needed. This hypothesis aligns with the observed increase in proloculus diameter during the mid-late LIG, which is associated with a higher prevalence of asexual reproduction—a likely adaptation to environments with stronger hydrodynamics. The reduction in morphological parameter variation may indicate increasingly restrictive living conditions during the late LIG. The whole period (128–119 ka BP) can be divided into two intervals: (a) early mid LIG (~128–123 ka BP) and (b) mid-late LIG (~123–119 ka BP).

1. early mid LIG (~128–123 ka BP, *blue shadow bar* in Figure 7): During the beginning of this stage (~2 ka), there was an increase of salinity, and the foraminiferal diversity was the highest over the LIG. The size-adjusted mass, surface area, surface area/volume ratio, ultimate chamber diameter, and the number of chambers display an increasing trend, suggesting an enhancement in calcification under a relatively ventilated and oxygenated environment compared to the mid-late LIG. *E. clavatum* was encountering high competition with other species, according to the diversity (Figure 7) and foraminiferal flux values of other species (Figure 5 in Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006). The wall thickness and pore density of the tests increased, while porosity and the abundance of *E. clavatum* decreased. This suggests that under relatively well-oxygenated and saline conditions during the early to mid-LIG, *E. clavatum* prioritized test solidity, enhancing its physical competitiveness during test formation. It agrees with the results indicating that an early LIG transgression and an increase in water depth in the North Sea-Baltic transition area led to relatively ventilated bottom waters in this section of the Danish Straits, with more frequent saline water exchanges from the North Sea compared to today (Ni et al., 2021). This was likely caused by a more open connection previously described in several former studies (Knudsen et al., 2011; Kristensen & Knudsen, 2006). The increasing trend of foraminiferal Ba/Ca (Figure 7b) may suggest an increase in freshwater input, nutrient supply and productivity which supported growth of the foraminifera (Gingele & Dahmke, 1994). There was an abrupt rise in salinity around 126 ka BP together with a high Ba/Ca and a decline in total foraminiferal flux as well as the flux of *E. clavatum*, suggesting a large freshwater pulse, however, this event was not clearly reflected in morphological signals, likely due to the sample resolution or because it had not yet affected the entire taxa or specific species. The bottom water salinity and foraminiferal diversity remained relatively high during 126–123 ka BP, while the total foraminiferal flux and the flux of *E. clavatum* were constantly low. This may reflect a recovery stage for the fauna from the large salinity variation, creating a more competitive environment for opportunistic species such as *E. clavatum* (Alve, 1995; Moodley & Hess, 1992). The test robustness of *E. clavatum* (characterized by high pore density, high wall thickness, and low porosity) remained relatively high.
2. mid-late LIG (~123–119 ka BP, *pink shadow bar* in Figure 7): the morphological parameters at each age interval exhibit less overall variation compared to that of other periods. A lower wall thickness and the highest porosity suggest that *E. clavatum* potentially adapted its morphology in response to decreased oxygen availability (Figure 7). Combining the results showing a decreasing foraminiferal assemblage diversity and bottom water salinity, it suggests a relatively stagnant and brackish bottom water condition. An interruption event occurred around ~122 ka BP, marked by a much more negative carbon isotope composition (a drop over 2‰) and sudden increases in temperature and salinity. This suggests that the Baltic Sea entrance experienced an influx of warm, saline, and relatively oxygenated and well-mixed water, resulting in high primary productivity. Consequently, *E. clavatum* adapted morphologically, emphasizing its test robustness by an increase in wall thickness and a decrease in porosity at 122 ka BP. The proloculus diameters were relatively higher

during the late LIG (~121–119 ka BP, Figure 7g), coinciding with the low salinity and diversity, and therefore low oxygen level during this period. This indicates that more rapid asexual reproduction may dominate in stressful environments for *E. clavatum*, resulting in a higher proportion of megalospheric individuals with larger proloculi, thereby increasing the survival rates of juveniles. This coincides with an intermittent high flux of *E. clavatum* during the same period, which may reflect the success of reproduction strategies they have applied.

5. Conclusions

We integrated *E. clavatum* 3D morphological features, derived from SR μ CT measurements, with foraminiferal assemblage and geochemistry to comprehensively explore the relationship between foraminiferal test structures, pore patterns, and the salinity and oxygen conditions during the last interglacial (LIG). Using *E. clavatum* proloculus diameter, pore density, porosity, wall thickness, flux, and fauna diversity, we reconstructed past bottom water oxygen levels and assessed environmental stress on foraminifera. We considered pore density and porosity, together with test wall thickness when exploring the impact of environmental conditions on foraminiferal morphological adaptation, regarding metabolism and mechanical constraints (i.e., gas uptake and test robustness). The integration of taxa diversity, species abundance, geochemical signals, and benthic foraminiferal morphology can be used together as a multiproxy approach for tracking long-term past seawater condition changes and relatively short-term major events. The proloculus diameter of *E. clavatum* is associated with its reproduction strategy (sexual or asexual reproduction modes) in response to environmental changes that enhance survival rates and support population growth.

During the LIG, low bottom water oxygen levels at Mommark were indicated by reduced foraminiferal diversity in the mid-late stage (123–119 ka BP) compared to the early mid stage (128–123 ka BP), along with an increased abundance of *E. clavatum*, an opportunistic infauna species adapted to low oxygen and salinity conditions. During the early LIG (128–126 ka BP), the wall thickness, pore density increased with enhanced calcification and decreased porosity, indicating a mechanical control or relatively higher dissolved oxygen availability under the early LIG transgression environment. During the mid-LIG (~126–123 ka BP), the mechanical constraints of *E. clavatum* remained relatively strong, possibly due to sustained mechanical demands or a relatively higher abundance of oxygen in the environment. The wall thickness, pore density, and the overall variations of morphological parameters were comparatively lower with a relatively higher porosity, during the mid-late LIG (123–119 ka BP). There was an interruption around 122 ka BP, a period with high salinity and warm North Sea inflows, was marked by negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, a Mn/Ca peak, a gap in *E. clavatum* abundance, and morphological changes (i.e., relatively higher wall thickness, and pore density, and lower porosity). Under low oxygen and salinity conditions, *E. clavatum* increased its porosity while decreasing pore density and wall thickness to prioritize gas exchange and maintain test mechanical integrity. The test mechanical integrity was reduced while oxygen extraction efficiency was enhanced by optimizing gas exchange under such stressful conditions during the latter half of the LIG.

Data Availability Statement

Data (supplementary Tables S1 and S2, and files of 3D SR-microCT scans) for this article can be found online at Ni (2024a, 2024b).

References

- Alve, E. (1995). Benthic foraminiferal responses to estuarine pollution; a review. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 25(3), 190–203. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsjfr.25.3.190>
- Andersen, S. T. (1975). The Eemian freshwater deposit at Egersund, South Jylland, and the Eemian landscape development in Denmark. *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse Årbog*, 49–70.
- Andrén, T., Björck, S., Andrén, E., Conley, D., Zillén, L., & Anjar, J. (2011). The development of the Baltic Sea Basin during the last 130 ka. In J. Harff, S. Björck, & P. Hoth (Eds.), *The Baltic Sea Basin. Central and Eastern European Development Studies (CEEDES)*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-17220-5_4
- Armstrong, H. A., & Brasier, M. D. (2005). *Microfossils* (2nd ed., p. 296). Blackwell Publishing.
- Bernhard, J. M. (1986). Characteristic assemblages and morphologies of benthic foraminifera from anoxic, organic-rich deposits; Jurassic through Holocene. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 16(3), 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsjfr.16.3.207>
- Brewer, S., Guiot, J., Sánchez-Goñi, M. F., & Klotz, S. (2008). The climate in Europe during the Eemian: A multi-method approach using pollen data. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 27(25–26), 2303–2315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2008.08.029>
- Burke, J. E., Renema, W., Henehan, M. J., Elder, L. E., Davis, C. V., Maas, A. E., et al. (2018). Factors influencing test porosity in planktonic foraminifera. *Biogeosciences*, 15(21), 6607–6619. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-15-6607-2018>

Acknowledgments

We thank the editor Matthew Huber, the associate editor, and the reviewers, Dr. J. Richirt and one anonymous, for their constructive and helpful comments and suggestions. We thank the European Union InterReg “MAX4ESSFUN” Cross Border Network and Researcher Programme, the Crafoord Foundation, the Carl Tryggers Foundation, the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation (SN), and the Swedish Research Council VR (2017-04190) for funding. We thank SPring-8 for beamtime under proposal numbers 2018B1241, and 2020A1221. We thank Kentaro Uesugi at the SPring-8 synchrotron facility (BL 47XU) as well as Kotaro Hirose at University of Hyogo and Yusuke Seto at Osaka Metropolitan University. We also acknowledge the Danish Council for Independent Research (Grants 7014-00113 B (G-Ice) and 0135-00165 B (GreenShelf) to MSS); the project has also received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant 869383 (ECOTIP) (MSS) and Grant 101136480 (SEA-Quester) (MSS). The foraminifera used in our analyses were from samples originally prepared in the laboratory by Svend Meldgaard Christiansen at Aarhus University. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

- Cheddadi, R., Mamakowa, K., Guiot, J., De Beaulieu, J. L., Reille, M., Andrieu, V., et al. (1998). Was the climate of the Eemian stable? A quantitative climate reconstruction from seven European pollen records. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, *143*(1–3), 73–85. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-0182\(98\)00067-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0031-0182(98)00067-4)
- Choquel, C., Mütter, D., Ni, S., Pirzamanbein, B., Charrieau, L. M., Hirose, K., et al. (2023). 3D morphological variability in foraminifera unravel environmental changes in the Baltic Sea entrance over the last 200 years. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, *11*, 1120170. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2023.1120170>
- Cignoni, P., Callieri, M., Corsini, M., Dellepiane, M., Ganovelli, F., & Ranzuglia, G. (2008). Meshlab: An open-source mesh processing tool. *Eurographics Italian chapter conference, 2008*, 129–136.
- Davis, C. V., Wishner, K., Renema, W., & Hull, P. M. (2021). Vertical distribution of planktic foraminifera through an oxygen minimum zone: How assemblages and test morphology reflect oxygen concentrations. *Biogeosciences*, *18*(3), 977–992. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-18-977-2021>
- Domander, R., Felder, A. A., & Doube, M. (2021). BoneJ2-refactoring established research software. *Wellcome Open Research*, *6*, 37. <https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.16619.1>
- Eiriksson, J., Kristensen, P. H., Lykke-Andersen, H., Brooks, K., Murray, A., Knudsen, K. L., & Glaister, C. (2006). A sedimentary record from a deep Quaternary valley in the southern Lillebælt area, Denmark: Eemian and Early Weichselian lithology and chronology at Mommark. *Boreas*, *35*(2), 320–331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480600612377>
- Fujimoto, N., Maruyama, H., Kawakami, Y., & Yamashita, T. (2018). Development of applications for aligned carbon nanotubes (HiTaCa). *Hit*, *79*, 59–63.
- Funder, S., & Balic-Zunic, T. O. N. C. I. (2006). Hypoxia in the Eemian: Mollusc faunas and sediment mineralogy from Cyprina Clay in the southern Baltic region. *Boreas*, *35*(2), 367–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480600612310>
- Gibbard, P., & Glaister, C. (2006). Pollen stratigraphy of the late Pleistocene sediments at Mommark, Als, South Denmark. *Boreas*, *35*(2), 332–348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480600612336>
- Gilbert, R. O. (1987). *Statistical methods for environmental pollution monitoring*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Gingele, F., & Dahmke, A. (1994). Discrete barite particles and barium as tracers of paleoproductivity in South Atlantic sediments. *Paleoceanography*, *9*(1), 151–168. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93pa02559>
- Glock, N., Eisenhauer, A., Milker, Y., Liebetrau, V., Schönfeld, J., Mallon, J., et al. (2011). Environmental influences on the pore density of *Bolivina spissa* (Cushman). *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, *41*(1), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsjfr.41.1.22>
- Glock, N., Erdem, Z., & Schönfeld, J. (2022). The Peruvian oxygen minimum zone was similar in extent but weaker during the Last Glacial Maximum than Late Holocene. *Communications Earth & Environment*, *3*(1), 307. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00635-y>
- Glock, N., Erdem, Z., Wallmann, K., Somes, C. J., Liebetrau, V., Schönfeld, J., et al. (2018). Coupling of oceanic carbon and nitrogen facilitates spatially resolved quantitative reconstruction of nitrate inventories. *Nature Communications*, *9*(1), 1217. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03647-5>
- Glock, N., Schönfeld, J., & Mallon, J. (2012). The functionality of pores in benthic foraminifera in view of bottom water oxygenation: A review. *Anoxia: Evidence for Eukaryote Survival and Paleontological Strategies*, 537–552. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1896-8_28
- Goldstein, S. T. (1999). Foraminifera: A biological overview. *Modern foraminifera*, 37–55. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-48104-9_3
- Govindankutty Menon, A., Davis, C. V., Nürnberg, D., Nomaki, H., Salonen, I., Schmiedl, G., & Glock, N. (2023). A deep-learning automated image recognition method for measuring pore patterns in closely related bolivinitids and calibration for quantitative nitrate paleo-reconstructions. *Scientific Reports*, *13*(1), 19628. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-46605-y>
- Groeneveld, J., & Filipsson, H. L. (2013). Mg/Ca and Mn/Ca ratios in benthic foraminifera: The potential to reconstruct past variations in temperature and hypoxia in shelf regions. *Biogeosciences*, *10*(7), 5125–5138. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-10-5125-2013>
- Groeneveld, J., Filipsson, H. L., Austin, W. E., Darling, K., McCarthy, D., Quintana Krupinski, N. B., et al. (2018). Assessing proxy signatures of temperature, salinity, and hypoxia in the Baltic Sea through foraminifera-based geochemistry and faunal assemblages. *Journal of Micro-paleontology*, *37*(2), 403–429. <https://doi.org/10.5194/jm-37-403-2018>
- Gupta, B. K. S., & Machain-Castillo, M. L. (1993). Benthic foraminifera in oxygen-poor habitats. *Marine Micropaleontology*, *20*(3–4), 183–201. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-8398\(93\)90032-s](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-8398(93)90032-s)
- Hallock, P. (1985). Why are larger foraminifera large? *Paleobiology*, *11*(2), 195–208. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0094837300011507>
- Hönisch, B., Allen, K. A., Russell, A. D., Eggins, S. M., Bijma, J., Spero, H. J., et al. (2011). Planktic foraminifera as recorders of seawater Ba/Ca. *Marine Micropaleontology*, *79*(1–2), 52–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2011.01.003>
- Iwasaki, S., Kimoto, K., Sasaki, O., Kano, H., Honda, M. C., & Okazaki, Y. (2015). Observation of the dissolution process of *Globigerina bulloides* tests (planktic foraminifera) by X-ray microcomputed tomography. *Paleoceanography*, *30*(4), 317–331. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014pa002639>
- Johnstone, H. J., Schulz, M., Barker, S., & Elderfield, H. (2010). Inside story: An X-ray computed tomography method for assessing dissolution in the tests of planktonic foraminifera. *Marine Micropaleontology*, *77*(1–2), 58–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2010.07.004>
- Kaiho, K. (1994). Benthic foraminiferal dissolved-oxygen index and dissolved-oxygen levels in the modern ocean. *Geology*, *22*(8), 719–722. [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1994\)022<0719:bfoia>2.3.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1994)022<0719:bfoia>2.3.co;2)
- Kinoshita, S., Kuroyanagi, A., Kawahata, H., Fujita, K., Ishimura, T., Suzuki, A., et al. (2021). Temperature effects on the shell growth of a larger benthic foraminifer (*Sorites orbiculus*): Results from culture experiments and micro X-ray computed tomography. *Marine Micropaleontology*, *163*, 101960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2021.101960>
- Knudsen, K. L., Jiang, H., Kristensen, P., Gibbard, P. L., & Haila, H. (2011). Early last interglacial palaeoenvironments in the western Baltic Sea: Benthic foraminiferal stable isotopes and diatom-based sea-surface salinity. *Boreas*, *40*(4), 681–696. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2011.00206.x>
- Knudsen, K. L., Kristensen, P., & Larsen, N. K. (2009). Marine glacial and interglacial stratigraphy in Vendsyssel, northern Denmark: Foraminifera and stable isotopes. *Boreas*, *38*(4), 787–810. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2009.00103.x>
- Kristensen, P. H., & Knudsen, K. L. (2006). Palaeoenvironments of a complete Eemian sequence at Mommark, South Denmark: Foraminifera, ostracods and stable isotopes. *Boreas*, *35*(2), 349–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480600612351>
- Kuhnt, T., Friedrich, O., Schmiedl, G., Milker, Y., Mackensen, A., & Lückge, A. (2013). Relationship between pore density in benthic foraminifera and bottom-water oxygen content. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, *76*, 85–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr.2012.11.013>
- Kuhnt, T., Schiebel, R., Schmiedl, G., Milker, Y., Mackensen, A., & Friedrich, O. (2014). Automated and manual analyses of the pore density-to-oxygen relationship in *Globobulimina turgida* (Bailey). *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, *44*(1), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsjfr.44.1.5>
- Kuroyanagi, A., Irie, T., Kinoshita, S., Kawahata, H., Suzuki, A., Nishi, H., et al. (2021). Decrease in volume and density of foraminiferal shells with progressing ocean acidification. *Scientific Reports*, *11*(1), 19988. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99427-1>

- Levin, L. A., Etter, R. J., Rex, M. A., Gooday, A. J., Smith, C. R., Pineda, J., et al. (2001). Environmental influences on regional deep-sea species diversity. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 32(1), 51–93. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.32.081501.114002>
- Lu, W., Wang, Y., Oppo, D. W., Nielsen, S. G., & Costa, K. M. (2022). Comparing paleo-oxygenation proxies (benthic foraminiferal surface porosity, I/Ca, authigenic uranium) on modern sediments and the glacial Arabian Sea. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 331, 69–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2022.06.001>
- Moodley, L., & Hess, C. (1992). Tolerance of infaunal benthic foraminifera for low and high oxygen concentrations. *The Biological Bulletin*, 183(1), 94–98. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1542410>
- Müller, H. (1974). Pollenanalytische Untersuchungen und Jahresschichtenzählungen an der eem-zeitlichen Kieselgur von Bispingen/Luhe. *Geologisches Jahrbuch*, 21, 149–169.
- Murray, J. W. (2006). *Ecology and applications of benthic foraminifera*. Cambridge University Press.
- Ni, S. (2024a). 3D micro-CT morphology data of benthic foraminifera in the Baltic Sea during the Last Interglacial [Dataset]. *Mendeley Data*, VI. <https://doi.org/10.17632/9fztrjc2d5.1>
- Ni, S. (2024b). 3D SRμCT scans of benthic foraminifera in the Baltic Sea during the last interglacial [Dataset]. *Mendeley Data*, VI. <https://doi.org/10.17632/7s7kgppzgz.1>
- Ni, S., Krupinski, N. Q., Chonewicz, J., Groeneveld, J., Knudsen, K. L., Seidenkrantz, M. S., & Filipsson, H. L. (2021). Seasonal climate variations in the Baltic Sea during the Last Interglacial based on foraminiferal geochemistry. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 272, 107220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2021.107220>
- Ni, S., Lu, Z., Zhang, Q., Groeneveld, J., Knudsen, K. L., Seidenkrantz, M. S., & Filipsson, H. L. (2023). Last interglacial seasonal hydroclimate in the North sea–baltic sea region. *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 312, 108152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2023.108152>
- Ni, S., Quintana Krupinski, N. B., Groeneveld, J., Fanget, A. S., Böttcher, M. E., Liu, B., et al. (2020). Holocene hydrographic variations from the Baltic-North Sea transitional area (IODP site M0059). *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology*, 35(2), e2019PA003722. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019pa003722>
- Pearson, P. N. (2012). Oxygen isotopes in foraminifera: Overview and historical review. *Paleontological Society Papers*, 18, 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s108933260002539>
- Petersen, J., Riedel, B., Barras, C., Pays, O., Guihéneuf, A., Mabilieu, G., et al. (2016). Improved methodology for measuring pore patterns in the benthic foraminiferal genus *Ammonia*. *Marine Micropaleontology*, 128, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2016.08.001>
- Polyak, L., Korsun, S., Febo, L. A., Stanovoy, V., Khusid, T., Hald, M., et al. (2002). Benthic foraminiferal assemblages from the southern Kara Sea, a river-influenced Arctic marine environment. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 32(3), 252–273. <https://doi.org/10.2113/32.3.252>
- Rathburn, A. E., Willingham, J., Ziebis, W., Burkett, A. M., & Corliss, B. H. (2018). A New biological proxy for deep-sea paleo-oxygen: Pores of epifaunal benthic foraminifera. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 9456. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-27793-4>
- Richirt, J., Champmartin, S., Schweizer, M., Mouret, A., Petersen, J., Ambari, A., & Jorissen, F. J. (2019). Scaling laws explain foraminiferal pore patterns. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 9149. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-45617-x>
- Schmiedl, G., Milker, Y., & Mackensen, A. (2023). Climate forcing of regional deep-sea biodiversity documented by benthic foraminifera. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 244, 104540. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2023.104540>
- Schneider, C. A., Rasband, W. S., & Eliceiri, K. W. (2012). NIH image to ImageJ: 25 years of image analysis. *Nature Methods*, 9(7), 671–675. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.2089>
- Shannon, C. E. (1948). A mathematical theory of communication. *The Bell system technical journal*, 27(3), 379–423. <https://doi.org/10.1145/584091.584093>
- Takahashi, K., & Allan, W. H. (1984). Planktonic foraminifera: Factors controlling sinking speeds. *Deep-Sea Research, Part A: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 31(12), 1477–1500. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0198-0149\(84\)90083-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0198-0149(84)90083-9)
- Tetard, M., Licari, L., & Beaufort, L. (2017). Oxygen history off Baja California over the last 80 kyr: A new foraminiferal-based record. *Paleoceanography*, 32(3), 246–264. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016pa003034>
- Titelboim, D., Lord, O. T., & Schmidt, D. N. (2021). Thermal stress reduces carbonate production of benthic foraminifera and changes the material properties of their shells. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 78(9), 3202–3211. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab186>
- Tyrrell, T., Schneider, B., Charalampopoulou, A., & Riebesell, U. (2008). Coccolithophores and calcite saturation state in the baltic and black seas. *Biogeosciences*, 5(2), 485–494. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-5-485-2008>
- Umling, N. E., Saad, B., Sikes, E., & Goodkin, N. F. (2021). Proximity to Undersaturation and the influences on *G. Bulloides* area-density in southern Indian Ocean marine sediments. *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology*, 36(6), e2021PA004249. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021pa004249>
- Wetmore, K. L. (1987). Correlations between test strength, morphology and habitat in some benthic foraminifera from the coast of Washington. *Journal of Foraminiferal Research*, 17(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsfjr.17.1.1>
- Zarkogiannis, S. D., Iwasaki, S., Rae, J. W. B., Schmidt, M. W., Mortyn, P. G., Kontakiotis, G., et al. (2022). Calcification, dissolution and test properties of modern planktonic foraminifera from the central Atlantic Ocean. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 864801. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.864801>